

Artificial Intelligence and the Role of the Architect: Defining Competence and Liability

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The Grenfell Tower fire, which claimed the lives of 72 people, remains one of the most shocking human tragedies in recent UK memory – and a stark reminder of what happens when safety and accountability fail.

Nearly eight years on, its impact continues to ripple through the construction and architecture industries, reshaping everything from building regulations to insurance. As these sectors grapple with heightened scrutiny, rising costs and evolving legal frameworks, a new wave of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools and algorithms is set to disrupt the landscape even further.

While AI can be harnessed to improve safety and accountability within architecture and construction, we are only just beginning to comprehend the new risks and uncertainties it introduces. Amid all of AI's potential positive contributions, one question stands out: who is responsible if AI gets it wrong? If an AI tool indicates that an architectural design is compliant with UK regulations, but that later turns out to be incorrect, does liability fall on the software user, the software developer, or the insurer? This case study delves into this very question, shedding light on the emerging challenges.

The Dual Nature of AI in Architecture

Professor Des Fagan is Head of Architecture at Lancaster University and a member of multiple committees at the Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA), the professional body best known to the public for its high-profile annual Stirling Prize. He joined *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub as an Expert-in-Residence after reading a [case study from the British Antarctic Survey](#), a previous collaborator of Practitioners Hub.

In his academic and industry roles, Professor Fagan is actively engaged in discussions around the concerns and challenges that inevitably accompany the rapid adoption of transformative technologies such as AI and Machine Learning (ML) – much of which is being developed without the direct input of those working day-to-day in the field. For building designers and contractors, those concerns include questions of liability and professional competence.

However, to understand the full impact of AI, we need to acknowledge its positive applications within

the field. AI is already being used (and will continue to be used) to make architects' lives easier and to enhance their practice, with hundreds of startups and tools occupying the space. Today's students are learning about and using these tools as part of their development into tomorrow's architects. Examples of real-world applications of AI, include the following:

- **Use of Generative AI that translates knowledge** such as from sketches or text prompts into different architectural styles. In 2019, [Stanislas Chaillou](#) authored a [project](#) that trained models on millions of historic building datasets to stylistically generate baroque and Victorian buildings from simple line drawings using Generative Adversarial Networks.
- **Development of surrogate models and digital twins** that can predict and monitor the sustainable and environmental performance of new buildings (such as daylight, noise or energy efficiency). In 2020, the Applied R+D group at [Foster + Partners](#) developed a [generative adversarial network \(GAN\)](#) to predict the performance of solar shading devices within milliseconds.
- **Automation of feedback systems** in areas including safety and regulatory compliance. In 2022, researchers from Loughborough University developed an [ML-based method for automated fire risk compliance](#) checking with building codes by directly interpreting raw building blueprints.
- **Training AI agents** to analyse buildings or streetscapes and identify areas for improvement. Start-up company, UrbanistAI, provides an [AI-based planning participation tool](#) for local governments and public interest groups to re-imagine and brainstorm new public spaces in cities.

Professor Fagan says: “AI’s value in architecture is clear – particularly when it comes to improving sustainability and efficiency. We can see there are huge opportunities in using AI to enhance design processes, automate time-consuming tasks, and improve decision-making.” The concerns, nonetheless, are real. As AI-driven design tools and compliance checkers are becoming more readily available to the public, regulators and insurers must confront the associated risks and responsibilities, ensuring technological advancement does not come at the expense of public safety or the professional integrity of the building sector.

Professor Fagan adds: “The key is making sure software users don’t simply adopt AI generated building design software without checks and balances, but use it in a way that aligns with professional standards, quality, and what I would describe as an architect’s ‘social contract’ to work for the public good. The UK architecture profession is regulated by the Architects Registration Board, which requires registered architects, a title protected by law, to maintain competency and act conscientiously with due regard to relevant technical and professional standards.

“Although this ensures a registered architect working on a building project will check the standards of quality and compliance of all their work, including that generated by AI tools, there remains a significant risk that non-architect users leverage AI tools to automate building designs that are not held to the same regulatory and professional standards. That’s what we’re exploring at the RIBA and in the Practitioners Hub.”

Professional Competence Redefined: Who Is Held Accountable?

One of the most pressing issues in AI-driven building design for architects is legal liability. When AI is used to generate designs, analyse structural integrity, assess energy efficiency or automate compliance checks, questions arise. To what extent should an architect understand the hidden processes behind these tools? Will detachment from the decision-making process lead to the potential erosion of professional competence over time, if architects lose oversight of how a decision has been made?

Traditionally, architects hold full control over their designs and decisions, balancing aesthetics, functionality and safety. However, with the use of ‘black box’ ML algorithms, it is not always clear how AI-generated outputs relate to their underlying inputs. In future, professional architects risk approving AI-influenced designs, including critical safety or compliance features, without fully understanding *how* they were achieved. Beyond legal implications – and as the use of AI tools grows – this brings into focus the need for improved transparency and interpretability for software tools if a decision is deemed to be high-risk.

Professor Fagan says: “The issue with architecture and design is that it’s a complex, analytical, subjective field with many possibilities – it’s rarely a case of a Boolean ‘yes or no’ that can be easily checked afterwards by a computer, due to the myriad of design possibilities. Our concern is with human decision-making that relies on outputs and advice from software where we aren’t party to the internal processes.” From the legal and insurance perspective, there’s an interesting parallel with driverless cars, where there are questions about the transfer of control and at which point the human or the software is deemed to be in charge.

“There are specific standards of professionalism and competency in architecture – similar to being a doctor or a lawyer. The introduction of software into the decision-making process raises questions for the sector, such as to what extent an architect can remain a competent professional if they rely on software to make their decisions, and where that competency and accountability ultimately lie – with the architect or with the software.”

Acceptance of AI-generated outputs without scrutiny could lead to accusations of incompetence if things go awry. To responsibly and effectively manage risks, the following approaches are recommended:

- AI and ML-based architectural tools should be transparent and explainable, providing architects with a rationale behind their recommendations, rather than opaque ‘black box’ algorithms that lack logical justification.
- At least in the short term, AI should be used as a complement to, and not a replacement for, traditional architectural skills and practices.
- Clear regulatory frameworks should be developed to define who holds responsibility for AI-assisted decisions – whether it’s the software user, the software provider, or through a new shared accountability model.
- Architectural training and education programmes should incorporate education on AI literacy and ethical considerations.
- Practices should retain and reinforce traditional QA procedures, updated to incor-

porate AI. Whilst AI can be used to generate or check information, a human should still be the final approver.

- Professional guidelines from organisations such as the RIBA should establish guidance or ‘ground rules’ for the adoption and implementation of AI into architectural practice – work currently ongoing as part of the RIBA AI and Data Expert Advisory Group.

This can only be achieved most effectively through an open and collaborative approach between different stakeholders, including architects, construction companies, material suppliers, software developers, insurers, regulators, and policymakers. Professor Fagan says: “We need to find ways to solve problems together because there’s no direct answer yet. AI is here to stay, but we must collectively decide how we all operate within this new landscape.” Some of these conversations have already begun with industry-led initiatives such as the Future AEC Software Specification, which sets out an idealised specification for future software tools for the AEC industry, including the responsible and appropriate use of AI.

Next Steps: Considerations for Standards, Processes and Transparency

As we move forward, careful consideration must be given to the following key areas:

Maintaining Quality and Safety: With the proliferation of automated AI-based building design tools and compliance checkers available to all, how will the government maintain quality and safety standards for the built environment in future, without careful regulation of building design and construction through the protection of function?

AI-Driven Application Processing: How will local building control, and planning departments process applications that are automated through generative AI, and can the same tools also help departments process their building approvals safely?

Architect Competency Verification: If architects are required to question the competency of team members who contribute to decision-making on building projects, how can they check the competencies of AI software agents without transparent tools to provide explanations?

Answering these questions will involve:

- evaluating the impact of AI tools on national and local authority building control and planning approvals to deliver a safe and high-quality UK-built environment of the future.
- collaborating with the new Building Safety Regulator to explore the impact of increased AI-based automated tools for building design and compliance to all – specifically, whether the ‘core’ activity of building design should be legally protected to guarantee the competencies described in the new Building Safety Act.
- building and understanding of new considerations required for professional indemnity insurance for architects using AI tools, providing clear guidance on cover and responsibilities.

- involving building design software developers to encourage transparent ML-based decision explanations for software users.

Key takeaways

- AI presents both opportunities and risks for architecture. AI is improving architectural practice and will make architects' lives easier through automation - but there are potential risks that demand scrutiny.
- Transparency and explainability are crucial for AI-based tools. To maintain professional control and ensure sound decision-making, architects need to understand the rationale behind AI's recommendations to maintain control and oversight.
- The integration of AI in architecture requires a reassessment of professional competence. Particularly, it demands balancing AI assistance with human oversight and intervention, as well as defining accountability mechanisms for AI systems.
- Regulatory frameworks and professional guidelines are needed to address the risks and responsibilities associated with AI's implementation in architecture. Organisations like RIBA are pioneering in this area by establishing guidance for the adoption and implementation of AI in architectural practice.
- Navigating the complexities of AI in architecture requires a collaborative effort involving architects, construction professionals, software developers, insurers, regulators, and policymakers, ensuring interdisciplinary and responsible development and adoption of AI, as championed by *The Turing Way* and its Practitioners Hub.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Prof Des Fagan

Prof. Des Fagan is the Head of Architecture at Lancaster University, with research interests in Optimisation and Deep Learning for Decision Support Systems in Design. He is particularly interested in the impact of Machine Learning on design processes and the regulatory and policy implications for the RIBA and ARB. As Chair of the National Practice and Policy Committee at the RIBA, Des oversees the development of policy and public affairs activities representing over forty thousand UK architects. He is a member of the Expert Advisory Group on Data and AI in Practice (RIBA) and leads the Working Group on AI in Architectural Education (SCOSA). Prior to academia, Des worked on several international award-winning projects, including as a Project Architect for the London Olympic Village 2012 and for the Glasgow Transport Museum at Zaha Hadid Architects.

Highlights from *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*

“I became involved with the Practitioners Hub through my interest in the work coming out of the Turing, particularly about the application of AI to environmental and sustainability questions. What initially drew me in was the opportunity to align with experts – I wasn’t necessarily looking to join a community but rather to gain insights from those at the forefront of AI research. That changed over time as I realised that, in many ways, we’re all working together to overcome the challenges of AI. The Practitioners Hub became a space for open discussion on the risks and opportunities AI presents in architecture and other fields, from automation to professional standards. The most valuable takeaways for me were the written toolkits shared through workshops including discussions

on structured approaches to risk management and communication. Engaging with other professionals and experts reinforced the importance of transparency and accountability as AI continues to shape our industry.”

Acknowledgements

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[The Turing Way](#) Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with [The Turing Way](#), please email: turing-way@turing.ac.uk.

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